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Editors: P. Bonifacio, F. Lucertini,
D. Romano & L. Sbordone

Preface

P. Bonifacio¹, F. Lucertini², D. Romano³, L. Sbordone²

¹LIRA, Observatoire de Paris, Université PSL, Sorbonne Université, Université Paris Cité,
CY Cergy Paris Université, CNRS, 5 place Jules Janssen 92195 Meudon, France

²European Southern Observatory, Alonso de Cordova 3109, Vitacura, Santiago, Chile

³INAF, Astrophysics and Space Science Observatory, Via Gobetti 93/3, 40129 Bologna, Italy

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Abstract

For a whole week, amidst the fabulous scenery of the Dolomites of Sexten (Italy), we enjoyed stimulating presentations and lively discussions on observations and theoretical interpretations of the abundances of CNOPS elements. We believe this was a very fruitful week, and in this collection of contributions, we have sought to capture the key topics covered during the workshop.

1 Introduction

We organised the workshop “Exploring the evolution of CNOPS elements from Earth and space” because we felt that in the current era of great observational and theoretical advances in the field of galaxy evolution—and in particular of the chemical evolution of galaxies—the CNOPS elements were somehow neglected. Furthermore, we noted that different communities were tackling the problem from various angles, but there was indeed little communication and cross-fertilisation between them. Hence, we decided to create an opportunity for those interested in these topics to come together, discuss, and exchange ideas.

2 Present and future

The conference afforded a broad and varied overview of current theoretical research into stellar evolution and nucleosynthesis, and the chemical and dynamical evolution of galaxies. At the same time, we followed the remarkable progress made in observations of CNOPS abundances in stars belonging to the various components of our Galaxy—including stellar streams—as well as in external galaxies at high and low redshift, in planets and planet-host stars, and in the interstellar medium.

Future directions point towards more self-consistent modelling of chemical evolution, relying on dedicated stellar evolution and nucleosynthesis models that capture all the essential sources of chemical elements. On the observational side, radio observations allow us to decipher the enrichment histories of rare isotopes that can not be accessed in stars. There is also much anticipation for new wide-field, ground-based spectroscopic surveys like WEAVE, 4MOST, and MOONS, alongside several space missions. The results of the fourth Gaia

data release are expected to facilitate a major step forward, significantly increasing the number of stars for which accurate parallaxes and proper motions are available, as well as those with useful spectra. There are also great expectations for the ESA PLATO mission, scheduled for launch this year, that holds the promise of providing accurate asteroseismic ages for many stars. Finally, JWST is already providing unprecedented information on high-redshift galaxies and their stellar populations; as data continue to accumulate in the coming years, they will certainly challenge our modelling capabilities. We heard also interesting highlights on future instruments: CUBES, ANDES ad HRMOS. Looking at the next decades, the high-resolution ELT spectrograph ANDES will allow to study objects that require high-sensitivity observations—Earth-like exoplanets and the first stars that shone in the early universe—while CUBES, mounted at the ESO VLT, will cover the UV band with high efficiency. HRMOS, being now proposed as a new instrument for the VLT, will offer a unique combination of very high resolution and multi-object capabilities, enabling the investigation of CNOPS elements in dense stellar systems.

We believe the next few years will yield many interesting results, and in three or five years' time it would be nice to meet again to discuss these new findings.

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